

DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES AND THE NEED TO INTRODUCE THEM INTO THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Annotation

The article discusses the need for the use of digital technologies in the educational process and the creation of conditions for the use of digital technologies to improve the quality of education. Modern digital technologies and the need to introduce them into the educational process are also considered.

Keywords

Digital technologies, construction, education system, distance learning process, cloud technologies, virtual reality, didactic materials,

Currently, modern digital technologies are actively used in all spheres of life (transport, construction, industry, service, Medicine, Education). In the minds of all citizens living in our country, including from young children to pensioners, the idea is being formed that with the help of digital technologies it is possible to solve all the problems of society. In addition, teachers achieve high results through the widespread use of modern digital technologies to increase students' interest in the subjects they study.

Special attention is paid to the problems associated with the use of modern digital technologies in our country, as well as the role of digital technologies being introduced in our lives, the protection of ethical and personal data, and the moral and legal aspects of competition arising between digitizing government organizations and employees of manufacturing enterprises [3].

Therefore, the process of development and modernization of the content and structure of the modern higher education system, on the one hand, is associated with the processes of informatization, and on the other, it is carried out within the framework of a competence-based approach. At the same time, the competence-based approach requires strengthening practical activities aimed at developing the ability to use scientific content in practical professional activities, the ability to solve professional problems using modern means of informatization. To achieve these goals, taking into account the global informatization of education, it is necessary to expand the sphere of competence of a graduate of a higher educational institution in the study of a specific educational process and to form it in the objects of information and professional activity [1].

We wanted to create conditions for the use of digital technologies to improve the quality of education. The content of modern educational and classical educational processes is such that when tablets or smartphones become part of learning, students are very interested in the learning process. As a result, the mutual integration of modern and classical education is ensured. As a result, the quality of education improves, the learner's assimilation and level of education increases. Personnel with modern knowledge is the key to the large—scale development of society.

Figure 1. The need to use digital technologies in the educational process

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The main driver of the economy of all developed and developing countries is manufacturing and industry. Therefore, who is responsible for the development of this economic system? Of course, the engineering staff, from the head to the smallest link working in this system, is considered responsible [2].

Of course, we all know that today all manufacturing and industrial technologies are digitalized and automated. Naturally, there is a need for personnel who can understand and use these technologies and thus make a worthy contribution to the development of the economy. This need in itself increases attention to the training and education of personnel, to the conditions created for them.

The training of future specialists in the areas of professional activity requires the creation of scientific and theoretical foundations for improving the quality of professional knowledge and experience, as well as the use of advanced pedagogical and psychological experience. To do this, it is necessary that students have an understanding of science, science and technology for everyone, regardless of which field of professional activity they choose in the future, and, of course, that we understand that all this is unthinkable without digital technologies and their development. In addition, it is necessary to understand that his independent social, political and economic views are important in this process, given that he also plays an important role in the changes and reforms taking place in the social and economic life of modern society.

In conclusion, let's say that this article examines in detail and provides examples from the historical period of mankind to modern digital technologies and their introduction into the educational process, as well as to the "fourth industrial revolution", decrees and decrees of the president and the government showed how relevant this topic is. Then the role of modern digital technologies in the educational process was analyzed, as well as the research works of Uzbek and foreign scientists on digital information technologies. As a result, the need for effective use of digital technologies in the educational process was listed, while maintaining the quality of education through the following structure.

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